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Nigeria's Economic Conundrum: Unpacking the Links: The Inflation-Consumption-Growth Nexus in Nigeria - An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

Steady increase in the average price of goods and services in a nation is known as inflation, and it has a significant impact on many facets of the economy, most notably private consumer spending and overall economic expansion. Therefore, using annual time series data gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and World Bank data for the years 1980 to 2023, this study investigates the relationship between inflation and private consumption spending in Nigeria. Descriptive statistics and the Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillips-Peron pre-test were used in the investigation. The study used the following independent variables: inflation, interest rates, private consumption expenditure, exchange rates, and real gross domestic product (RGDP) as the dependent variable. The findings showed that economic growth will decrease by 148.03 percent and 80.05 percent, respectively, for every 10% increase in inflation and private consumption spending. According to the study's findings, Nigeria's economic growth was significantly impacted by both inflation and private consumption spending. The findings recommend, the government should combat inflation and stabilize prices while making sure that spending is focused on items that would promote economic expansion.

Keywords: *Inflation, Private consumption spending, Economic growth, Nigeria, Time series analysis Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)*

1.1 Background to the Study: Conundrum

Final consumption expenditures for households are referred to as household consumption expenditures. It is the market worth of all commodities and services, including long-lasting items that households buy, such as cars, washing machines, and home computers. Imputed rent for owner-occupied homes is included, while purchases of homes are not. Payments and fees to governments for obtaining licenses and permissions are also included. (Osuji, Obinna, 2020). Given that household consumption expenditures make up the largest portion of total consumption expenditures in Nigeria and account for over 65% of GDP (National Bureau of Statistics, 2010), it is imperative to investigate the relationship between inflation and household consumption expenditures. Most governments concentrate on guaranteeing a higher standard of living and a consistent rate of economic growth since household consumption expenditure is a key component of aggregate demand and is crucial to the economy of any country. Inflation is one of the major issues Nigeria, one of Africa's biggest countries, faces amid many other economic difficulties. Wide-ranging effects on many facets of the economy, especially private consumer spending and overall economic growth, result from inflation, which is defined as a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in a nation over an extended period of time (Umaru and Zubairu 2012).

The central bank of Nigeria (CBN) has considered attaining price stability its primary monetary policy goal and views it as an essential component of macroeconomic policy. Umaru and Zubairu (2012) state that, among other things, the emphasis on price stability in monetary policy conduct is intended to support sustained growth and development by bolstering the native currency's purchasing power. When implementing monetary policy, the central bank uses the monetary targeting strategy. This is predicated on the idea that the money supply and inflation have a steady and predictable connection.

High inflation in Nigeria is having an impact on the country's economy and society. Each unit of currency may purchase fewer goods and services as real income declines because of the currency's declining buying power. Increased production costs have resulted in increased pricing for consumers, who already have less discretionary income. Workers, particularly those in the public sector, are now demanding higher wages because of the nation's strong inflation tendency. Economic growth has also been

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negatively impacted by a fall in the motivation to save and invest. (Isaiah & Udoh, 2018). Notwithstanding these initiatives, inflation has remained a major obstacle to the expansion and advancement of the Nigerian economy.

In macroeconomic theory, the connection between inflation, consumption, and economic growth has been a contentious topic that policymakers continue to discuss. Vinayagathan (2013) asserts that the impact of inflation on real production growth is contingent upon its impact on the amount of investment and savings over the short and long term, respectively. With a particular focus on Nigeria, this study uses a country-specific methodology to examine if inflation is harmful to a nation's economic development. By carrying out a methodical examination of how inflation affects economic development and private consumer spending. In order to support price stability, maintain consumer confidence, and promote sustainable economic development in Nigeria, this study aims to offer important insights into the intricate relationship between inflation, private consumption spending, and economic growth. It also aims to contribute to the formulation of effective monetary and fiscal policies. Therefore, the goal of the study is to ascertain how inflation affects Nigeria's economic growth as well as how private consumption expenditure affects it. It is anticipated that the results of this study would help stakeholders, economists, and policymakers create methods that effectively control inflation and promote economic growth in Nigeria.

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FIG. 1: Recent trend in inflation rate (IR), money supply (M2), gross domestic product (GDP) and exchange rate (ER) in Nigeria.

Source: Author's computation

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual literature

Inflation

According to Lipsey and Chrystal (1995), inflation is characterized as a widespread price increase that lasts for an extended length of time in an economy; in other words, a steady increase in the cost of goods and services that reduces the purchasing power of the currency. Buying power, or the actual tangible items that money can purchase, is how the worth of the Naira is determined (Abang, Arasomwan & Ayodele 2024). The consumer price index, which represents the annual percentage change in the average

consumer's cost when purchasing a basket of goods and services—which may be set or fluctuate periodically, usually on an annual basis—is used to monitor inflation.

Private Consumption Expenditure

The entire amount of money spent by individuals and families on products and services for their personal consumption is referred to as private consumption expenditure or household consumption expenditure. Food, clothing, housing, transportation, healthcare, education, entertainment, and other personal and domestic essentials are just a few of the many things it covers. Private spending, which represents the consumption component of the expenditure approach to computing GDP, is a crucial part of aggregate demand in an economy. It shows how much money households spend on consumption, which is impacted by a number of variables, including disposable income, consumer confidence, borrowing costs, and projections about the state of the economy.

Economic Growth

Economic growth is another crucial idea that captures the focus of this essay. On the other hand, Dwivedi (2004) defines economic growth as a long-term, steady rise in net national product or per capita national output. It suggests that the overall output growth rate must outpace the population growth rate. The composition of national output should consist of commodities and services that meet the needs of the greatest number of people. This is another way to measure economic growth. The quantitative rise in the monetary worth of goods and services generated in an economy over a specific year is known as economic growth. A percentage change in the economy is used to quantify economic growth, Gross Domestic Product or Gross National Product (Dwivedi, 2004).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Theories of inflation

- a. The quantity theory of money, or monetarist approach: This is the connection between the velocity of circulation of the money supply and national income as determined by market prices. The money supply and price levels have a positive relationship. This relationship is represented by the equation $MV=PY$, where Y is the total income, M is the total quantity of money in circulation, V is the velocity of circulation, and P is the general level of prices.

As a result, there will be a proportionately positive relationship between an economy's money supply and price levels. In other words, price levels will rise by the same percentage if the money supply increases by a specific amount. According to this theory, an increase in a nation's money supply is what causes inflation. It is believed that an increase in the money supply that is not followed or maintained by an increase in the money supply is what causes inflationary conditions.

- b. The Keynesian theory of inflation: John Maynard Keynes developed this hypothesis in 1919. One could consider the Keynesian inflation theory to be a generalization and extension of Wicksell's perspective. Keynes believed that a rise in aggregate demand may result from an increase in real factors. Keynes defined the inflationary gap as the discrepancy between the output that is available at full employment and the predicted expenditure. According to Keynes, an increase in aggregate demand that outpaces an increase in aggregate supply is what causes inflation, or an increase in general price levels. A rise in government expenditure (G), private consumption (C), and private investment (I) will raise aggregate demand, which will raise general price levels if an economy's output is at full employment. When an economy cannot increase its output or aggregate supply in response to a rise in aggregate demand at its optimal or full employment level (maximum utilization of limited resources), an inflationary situation like this occurs.

FIG 2: Inflationary Gap

FIG. 3: Structural Inflation

Figure 2 illustrates how the aggregate demand curve shifts upward, with $C + I + G + \Delta G$ representing the excess demand at full employment output, or AB. AB: The amount that aggregate demand surpasses aggregate output at full employment is known as the inflationary gap. Since the output cannot be increased above full employment, prices will rise, leading to demand-pull inflation. Y_f : is Equilibrium Output or Full Employment Output. In order to reach point B, where it crosses the 45-degree line, aggregate demand must move downward. Thus, this can be achieved by passing appropriate legislation, like tax increases or spending reductions.

- a. The Structural Theory of Inflation: This hypothesis states that the inelasticity of the economic structures is the primary source of inflation. The nature and foundation of inflation in developing nations are mainly explained by this theory. These factors include inelasticities in the agricultural sector, labor force and employment structures, capital formulation, production level and capacity, and institutional framework. According to the idea, the economy's slower and more erratic export growth rate, which is ineffective in sustaining the necessary economic growth rate, is the cause of the rise in inflation. Additionally, according to this idea, the service sector must experience ongoing cost pressures if money salaries expand at a consistent rate across the economy. This is thought to have slower growth in productivity. Consequently, supply inelasticities that raise agricultural prices and expenses are the cause of structural inflation.

2.2.2 Theories of Economic Growth

- a. Classical Growth Theory: Economists like Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and Thomas Malthus developed the classical growth theory, commonly referred to as the classical model of economic growth, in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. It establishes the framework for comprehending economic growth in light of elements including labor force expansion, technical advancement, and capital accumulation. Classical economists placed a strong emphasis on how investment and saving contribute to economic expansion. They held that over time, higher levels of productivity and income result from greater capital accumulation brought about by investments in tangible capital like infrastructure and machines. Classical economists frequently saw technical innovation as a slow, exogenous

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process, even if they acknowledged its significance in promoting growth. It was believed that technological advancements would boost productivity and efficiency, which would support sustained economic growth.

- b. Neo-Classical growth theory: A major advancement over classical growth theory, neoclassical growth theory—also referred to as the Solow-Swan model—arose in the middle of the 20th century. Economists Trevor Swan and Robert Solow were principally responsible for its development. Neoclassical thinkers, like classical economists, place a strong emphasis on how capital accumulation propels economic expansion. They did, however, introduce the idea of diminishing returns to capital, which postulates that as capital accumulates, its marginal production falls. Like classical growth theory, neoclassical growth theory includes technological advancement as an exogenous component. However, rather than concentrating only on output levels, it also examines the impact of technical advancement on the economy's long-term growth rate.

Because of declining returns to capital, economies with lower amounts of capital per worker are expected to grow more quickly, according to the Solow-Swan model. As a result, convergence is predicted, whereby poorer nations eventually overtake wealthier nations as they increase their investments in tangible capital.

- c. Endogenous growth theory: By stressing that technical advancement and innovation are endogenous, or internally determined, rather than exogenous, endogenous growth theory departs from neoclassical models. This implies that the rate of technological progress and, consequently, economic growth can be influenced by economic policies, investments in human capital, research and development, and other elements within the economic system itself.

According to proponents of endogenous growth theory, innovation and knowledge are key factors in economic expansion. According to endogenous growth theory, investments in R&D, education, and human capital can result in long-term increases in productivity and economic output, in contrast to neoclassical models that see technological advancement as exogenous. Increasing returns to scale, which state that production of products and services becomes

more efficient as manufacturing scales up, are frequently included in endogenous growth models. This raises the prospect of steady, long-term economic growth free from declining returns on capital accumulation.

2.2.3 Theories of Consumption

a. **Relative income theory of consumption**

Keynes's theory of consumption led Duesenberry to conclude that an individual's consumption is based on a previously achieved income level rather than his present income. Duesenberry's relative income hypothesis states that a person's consumption is determined by his or her relative position in the income distribution of a society rather than by their absolute income; in other words, an individual's consumption is influenced by how much money they make in comparison to other members of the society. For instance, his relative income would stay the same even though his absolute income would have climbed if everyone in a society had their salaries rise by the same amount. According to Duesenberry, a person will continue to spend the same percentage of his income on consumption as he did prior to the absolute increase in his income since his relative income has stayed the same. In other words, even though his absolute income has increased, his average propensity to spend (APC) will not change.

b. **Life-cycle theory of consumption**

Another post-Keynesian idea is this one. According to Modigliani's theory, consumption in any given era is determined by lifetime expected income rather than the income of the time. Therefore, according to the life cycle theory, a person plans their consumption expenditures according to their predicted lifetime income. Furthermore, it is expected that a person's intake remains relatively constant or perhaps slightly increases. According to Modigliani, the life cycle model's starting point is the theory that households' choices about saving and consumption at each stage of life represent a more or less deliberate effort to achieve the desired distribution of consumption over the life cycle subject to the constraint imposed by the resources accruing to the household over its lifetime.

c. **Permanent income theory of consumption**

The Life Cycle method and Milton Friedman's Income Theory of Consumption are similar in that Friedman concluded that consumption is influenced by income over the long term rather than by current income levels. People base their plans for consumption on this long-term expected income, which Friedman refers to as a permanent income. Friedman asserts that a person who only gets paid or receives revenue once a week—for example, on Friday—would not focus all of his spending on that day and have no consumption on any other day of the week. He contends that a person would rather have a steady flow of consumption each day than have a lot of spending today and little tomorrow. Therefore, revenue earned on a certain day does not determine consumption on that day. Rather, it is based on the average daily revenue during a given time period. The life cycle idea is supported by this.

According to him, people plan their consumption based on what Friedman refers to as permanent income—the projected average income over an extended period of time. According to this idea, economic measures may not have a multiplier effect on increased consumer spending even if they are successful in raising economic revenue. Instead, the argument states that unless workers adjust their expectations regarding their future earnings, consumer spending will not increase. In contrast to Keynesian economics, which suggested that people should base their consumption on their immediate after-tax income, Milton thought that individuals should base their consumption on an estimate of their future income. Milton's premise was that people would rather smooth their consumption than allow it to fluctuate because of the short-term fluctuations in income.

2.3 **Empirical Literature**

Many studies have been conducted throughout the years to look at how inflation affects economic growth, but very few have looked at how it affects private spending. First, we examine the body of research on the Nigerian example and from a worldwide viewpoint.

Foreign Evidence

Barro (1995) used data from 1960–1970 to evaluate the impact of inflation on the economic performance of more than 100 nations worldwide. According to the study's regression analysis, if several countries' characteristics remain unchanged, a ten percent annual increase in average inflation lowers the real GDP growth rate by 0.2 to 0.3 percent and the investment-to-GDP ratio by 0.4 to 0.6 percent.

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In their 1995 study on the factors influencing economic growth, Bruno and Easterly defined high inflation crises as "periods when annual inflation is above 40%" using a nonparametric approach. With an inflation rate of 40 percent and higher as the threshold for an inflation crisis, the authors used annual data for 26 countries to identify those with high inflation crises. They then evaluated the growth performance of these countries prior to, during, and following their high inflation crises. After adjusting for additional variables such as shocks from wars, political crises, and terms of trade, the study's findings demonstrated a negative correlation between inflation and growth.

Prasanna and Gopakumar (2009) used the co-integration and error correction models to investigate the empirical link between inflation and economic growth in India from 1972 to 2007. Their study's empirical findings demonstrated a negative correlation between inflation and economic growth. Second, growth is less sensitive to changes in inflation rates than inflation is to changes in growth rates.

De Mello and Carneiro (2010) examined spending patterns in an environment of consistently high inflation using consumption functions modeled after the Euler equation. The empirical results showed that consumption volatility is caused by broad backward-looking indexation and entire foreign currency substitution through dollarization when there is consistently high inflation. Accordingly, the study came to the conclusion that somewhat similar underlying consumer spending reactions to shocks are necessary if external shocks are to have a comparable effect on Latin American countries with high inflation.

Alem and Soderbo (2010) used panel data to study household-level consumption in urban Ethiopia: the effects of idiosyncratic shocks and inflation in food prices. Their study's findings indicated that the inflation of food prices had a negative impact on households with low asset levels. Additionally, they discovered that homes with casual employment were more susceptible to shocks to food prices.

Wadal (2011) conducted an econometric analysis of the private consumption function in Lebanon, looking at how consumption in the country responded to wealth, inflation, interest rates, and income. The primary drivers of real private consumption in Lebanon were investigated using a data set spanning the years 1975–2007 using actual factors rather than nominal variables. The study's findings showed that wealth, projected inflation, and current disposable income all impacted real private consumption over the long term.

Agalega and Acheampong (2013) used a co-integration approach with annual time series data covering the years 1980–2010 to investigate the effects of inflation,

policy rate, and government consumption expenditure on GDP growth in Ghana. The study's findings demonstrated a long-term positive correlation between real GDP, policy rate, and inflation; conversely, government consumption spending had a long-term negative effect on real GDP. The outcome also showed that government consumer spending and inflation had a short-term beneficial impact on real GDP. In order to demonstrate the economy's growth, the study concluded by recommending, among other things, that the government, acting through the Bank of Ghana, create and implement sound fiscal and monetary policies that would seek to stabilize and lower both macro and microeconomic indicators, particularly inflation targeting.

Nigerian Evidence

Nwabueze (2009) examined the causal relationship between personal consumption spending and gross domestic product by analyzing the Nigerian case. Regression analysis was used in the study to examine the causal association between Nigeria's gross domestic product and personal consumption expenditures using annual data from 1994 to 2007. The findings demonstrated that while rising consumption spending would raise GDP, rising GDP would not raise household consumption expenditure.

Chimobi (2010) used annual data from 1970 to 2005 to examine the connection between inflation and economic growth. The two factors did not co-integrate, according to the study. However, the study demonstrated a unidirectional correlation between inflation and economic growth using Granger causality tests. Odior (2011) used data from 1980 to 2008 using reduced form coefficients of the simultaneous equation model to investigate the household welfare impact of macroeconomic volatility on private consumption (PCE) in Nigeria. The findings demonstrated that macroeconomic instability does cause consumption spending to drop and that the impacts of inflation on the PCE are more pronounced over a longer time horizon. The study came to the conclusion that welfare is negatively impacted by inflation.

Osuala and Onyeike (2013) used Granger causality and a data set covering 1970–2011 to investigate how inflation affected economic growth in Nigeria. The empirical findings demonstrated a statistically significant positive correlation between Nigeria's economic growth and inflation. The link between Nigeria's inflation and economic growth, however, lacks a leading variable. The effect is simultaneous, they conclude.

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Shuaib et al. (2015) used secondary data from 1960 to 2012 to investigate how Nigeria's inflation rate affected economic growth. According to the test's empirical findings, there was no co-integrating link between inflation and economic growth within the study's time frame for Nigerian data. Furthermore, there was no causal connection between inflation and economic growth, according to the Granger causality test.

On the other hand, Umaru and Zubairu (2012) argue that inflation boosts output, productivity, and total factor productivity, all of which have a beneficial impact on economic growth. Using panel data analysis.

Oduh (2012) investigated how Nigerian consumers' expectations and confidence affected their consumption. The study examined the macroeconomic factors that influence private consumption, focusing on consumer expectations and confidence while taking into consideration differences among Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. The results demonstrated a strong positive correlation between household planned spending and consumer confidence. The biggest factor influencing consumption, aside from currency rates, is consumer confidence, which accounts for 3.2% of the change in anticipated expenditure and 1.7% of the total.

Saviour, Ferdinand and Jacob (2022) investigated the effects of selected macroeconomic variables on stock market performance in Nigeria. The study employed time-series data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin and World Development Indicators. Stock market performance was measured using the all-shares index, while the identified macroeconomic variables included GDP growth, broad money supply, exchange rate, savings interest rate, and mostly inflation rate. An Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) estimation technique was used to establish the long run relationship among the variables, and it was revealed that a long run relationship existed among the variables in the estimated model. The result shows that macroeconomic variables such as gross domestic product, broad money supply, exchange rate, and savings interest rate have a positive effect on stock market performance in Nigeria. On the other hand, the results showed that the inflation rate has a negative effect on stock market performance in Nigeria. Predicated on the result, the study recommended that policies to increase gross domestic product, exchange rate, interest rate, and money supply should be implemented because they can lead to an improvement in the performance of the stock market, while the inflation rate should be maintained at a single digit to prevent its negative effect on the performance of the stock market in Nigeria.

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Saviour, Ekpe, & Salamat (2023) in their study examined the impact of monetary policy and real exchange rate volatility in Nigeria. The study used time series data obtained from CBN and the World Bank in 2021, and the ordinary least squares (OLS) statistical technique was used to assess the degree of influence that the variables have on each other. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was adopted to test for unit roots, and Johansen's co-integration test was also conducted to establish long run association. The study also incorporates one co-integrating equation, the vector error correction model (VECM), the Granger causality test, and the CUSUM test for further analysis. The study reveals that real exchange rate volatility has a negative and insignificant effect on real GDP in Nigeria. It also shows that monetary policy has a positive and insignificant influence in the Nigerian economy. The study shows (among others) that there is no long run or short run relationship from real effective exchange rate volatility, domestic interest rate, government spending and Net export running to real GDP. This study therefore suggests that the government should implement an expansionary monetary policy through an increase in money supply by reducing the domestic interest rate. The government should implement an exchange rate system that is market-determined and should step in only at crucial times to ensure stability in the exchange rate.

Chude and Chude (2015) used the OLS analysis technique to examine the association between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria between 2000 and 2009. The results reveal that inflation and economic growth in Nigeria are strongly correlated, that the exchange rate has a positive effect on economic growth, and that high interest rates have a negative effect on growth.

3 Research Methodology

Research Design

Time-series data is used in the current study's quantitative research design. The study provides a quantitative explanation of how inflation and consumption expenditure are related. The ordinary least squares (OLS) test is used to examine the long-term effects of inflation on consumption expenditure. The objective is to make decisions in real life based on the statistical findings. In order to perform thorough research and get an accurate result through statistical analysis, the quantitative research method was employed. The OLS test is used to examine the connection between inflation and private consumption expenditures.

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The general functional form of the linear regression model is stated below:

$$RGDP=f(INF, PCE, INTR, EXR) \quad (1)$$

Where;

RGDP= Real Gross Domestic Product

INF = Inflation

PCE = Private Consumption Expenditure

INT = Interest Rate

EXR = Exchange Rate

f= functional relationship

From equation (1), the formula is further stated in an econometric form as:

$$RGDP= \beta_0 + \beta_1 INF + \beta_2 PCE + \beta_3 INT + \beta_4 EXR + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where: β_0 = Intercept of relationship in the model/ constant;

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of each independent or explanatory variable;

ε = Stochastic Error term

Estimation Techniques

An econometrics statistical program (E-Views 11) was used for estimation. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) approach was used to estimate our model. We used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test to test for stationarity of the series because we are using annualized time-series data, and the study covers a long sample period. This ensured that our data set was not impacted by unit root. All of the data used in this paper came from secondary sources. Finding suitable published data is essential to getting incredibly dependable outcomes. The Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletins and the National Bureau of Statistics provided us with the data.

4 Data presentation analysis and discussion of findings

Descriptive Statistics

The series' highest and lowest values over the studied period are known as the maximum and minimum. The maximum values for RGDP, INF, PCE, INTR, and EXR are 77001.48, 72.81, 57.70, 23.24, and 638.70, respectively, according to Table 1 below. RGDP, INF, PCE, INTR, and EXR, on the other hand, have minimum values of 13779.26, 4.67, -22.38, 5.39, and 0.55, respectively. The spread or dispersion of the series is measured by the standard deviation. The standard deviations for RGDP, INF,

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PCE, INTR, and EXR are 22582.27, 15.54, 14.77, 3.80, and 136.08, respectively, according to table 1 below. This indicates that while interest rates (INTR) have a small spread over time, real gross domestic product has the biggest spread during the study period.

The probability distribution of a real-valued random variable with respect to its mean is measured by its skewness. At zero, a normal distribution is symmetrical. A value is said to be positively skewed if it exceeds zero and negatively skewed if it falls below zero. Table 1 shows that the skewness of all the variables is positive. Kurtosis quantifies how flat or peaky the series' distribution is. The distribution is flat or platykurtic in relation to the normal if the kurtosis is less than three and peaked or leptokurtic if it is greater than three. With the exception of real gross domestic product (RGDP), which is partially because of the conversion to natural logarithm, all of the variables in Table 1 are above three. A test statistic called Jarque-Bera is used to determine whether the series has a normal distribution. According to Table 1, the relative Jarque-Bera values for RGDP, INF, PCE, INTR, and EXR are 5.36, 46.03, 18.70, 9.89, and 33.83. The null hypothesis, according to which the residual of the variables is normally distributed with zero means and constant variance, is rejected because the probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistic for each of the variables (RGDP, INF, PCE, INTR, and EXR) was less than the 5% level of significance.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	RGDP	INF	PCE	INTR	EXR
Mean	37976.47	18.45230	5.005292	11.07181	130.1521
Median	27112.63	12.79500	4.110838	9.731551	115.2551
Maximum	77001.48	72.81000	57.70378	23.24167	638.7000
Minimum	13779.26	4.670000	-22.37807	5.388750	0.546781
Std. Dev.	22582.27	15.54446	14.77422	3.795421	136.0771
Skewness	0.500257	1.961251	1.086681	1.010139	1.575969
Kurtosis	1.612804	6.118002	5.339638	4.146925	5.919105
Jarque-Bera	5.363127	46.03125	18.69525	9.894422	33.83579
Probability	0.028456	0.000000	0.000087	0.007103	0.000000

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Sum	1670965.	811.9010	220.2329	487.1598	5726.692
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.192290	10390.10	9385.940	619.4245	796230.2
Observations	44	44	44	44	44

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Stationarity (Unit root) test

The stationarity (unit root) test result is displayed in Table 2. The purpose of the unit root test was to determine the variables' stationarity conditions. The Phillips-Perron and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests served as the test's foundations. All of the variables (RGDP, INF, PCE, INTR, and EXR) were stationary at level I(0), according to the test results shown in table 2. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) approach, also known as the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE), is used to estimate the model or equation based on the results of the stationarity test. Additionally, figure 4 displays each variable's graph as it appears in the model. The graph shows that the variables have a trend, and as such, the stationarity of the variables can be checked.

Table 2: Unit root test result using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron tests

Variables	ADF			Phillips-Perron		
	Level	1 st Difference	Order of Integration	Level	1 st Difference	Order of Integration
RGDP	-3.184453	-	I(0)	-2.889639	-	I(0)
EXR	-4.626873	-	I(0)	-3.657512	-	I(0)
PCE	-6.727139	-	I(0)	-6799496	-	I(0)
INF	-4.493522	-	I(0)	-4.886802	-	I(0)
INTR	-3.880641	-	I(0)	-2.903330	-	I(0)

ADF test critical test values.

Level:

At 5per cent = -2.931404

10per cent = -2.603944

Phillip-Peron test critical values

Level: :

At 5per cent = -2.931404

10per cent = -2.603944

Source: Author's computation using Eviews 10 (2024)

FIG. 4: Individual trend graph of the variables

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Granger Causality

Table 3's findings indicate that the real gross domestic product (RGDP) and exchange rate (EXR) have a unidirectional relationship. GDP is caused by EXR Granger with feedback. This indicates that reducing the rate of inflation and the amount spent on private consumption will boost Nigeria's economy. This indicates a causal relationship between EXR and RGDP. At the five percent significance level, both the p-value and the F-statistic are statistically significant. Exchange rates consistently play a major role in driving Nigeria's economic expansion. The null hypothesis, according to which the

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exchange rate has no Granger effect on real gross domestic product, was thus disproved. This suggests that EXR either raises or lowers RGDP. Due to their unidirectional relationship with economic growth (RGDP), private consumption expenditure (PCE) and inflation (INF) are comparable. This indicates a causal relationship between PCE and RGDP as well as between INF and RGDP.

At the five percent significance level, the inflation (INF) and private consumption expenditure (PCE) p-values and associated F-statistics are statistically significant. The null hypothesis, according to which inflation and private consumption expenditure (PCE) do not Granger produce economic growth (RGDP), was thus disproved. This suggests that changes in inflation (INF) and private consumption expenditure (PCE) influence changes in economic growth (RGDP). On the other hand, interest rates (INTR) and GDP growth are not causally related. It demonstrates that without feedback, INTR has no effect on economic growth (RGDP). At the five percent significance level, the interest rate (INTR) p-value and F-statistic are not statistically significant. Therefore, it was decided to accept the null hypothesis that interest rates (INTR) do not Granger induce economic growth (RGDP). This suggests that interest rates have no effect on the growth or decline of economic growth (RGDP).

Table 3: Granger causality

Lags: 2

Null Hypotheses:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Decision
EXR does not Granger Cause RGDP	42	4.26646	0.0275	Reject
RGDP does not Granger Cause EXR		1.17130	0.3212	Accept
PCE does not Granger Cause RGDP	42	3.61909	0.0367	Reject
RGDP does not Granger Cause PCE		0.63659	0.5348	Accept
INF does not Granger Cause RGDP	42	3.19683	0.0222	Reject
RGDP does not Granger Cause INF		1.74216	0.1892	Accept
INTR does not Granger Cause RGDP	42	0.14228	0.8679	Accept
RGDP does not Granger Cause INTR		2.15458	0.1303	Accept

Source: Author's computation (2024)

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Correlation Matrix

The correlation values, which quantify the strength of the linear link between each pair of variables, are displayed in the correlation matrix. The range of correlation values is -1 to +1. A totally negative linear correlation between two variables is denoted by a value of -1. There is no linear association between two variables when the value is 0. A totally positive linear correlation between two variables is denoted by a value of 1. All of the variables that enter the model are perfectly positive and correlated, according to the results displayed in Table.

Table 4: Correlation matrix

	RGDP	EXR	PCE	INF	INTR
RGDP	1.000000				
EXR	0.876633	1.000000			
PCE	0.123736	0.229160	1.000000		
INF	-0.287284	-0.201216	0.061294	1.000000	
INTR	-0.345444	-0.243359	0.136547	0.399291	1.000000

Source: Author's computation (2024)

4.2 Presentation of result

Ordinary Least Square result

The findings of the analysis in our study based on the OLS are displayed in the regression as displayed in Table 5. In addition to displaying the relationship between the dependent and explanatory variables, the RGDP result was regressed on the explanatory variables of interest rate (INT), inflation rate (INF), private consumption expenditure (PCE), and exchange rate (EXR). A decent fit is indicated by the R2 and Adj R2 values of 0.74 and 0.69, respectively. The Cochrane-Orcutt iterative was adopted since the Durbin-Watson statistic for the result was low (0.88), indicating the presence of autocorrelation.

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Table 5: OLS Result Dependent Variable: GNPPC

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	0.145792	0.747806	0.194960	0.8466
PCE	-129.0412	44.54647	-2.896778	0.0065
INF	-4.777758	2.856333	-1.672689	0.1033
INT	-19.68494	11.34380	-1.735304	0.0915
C	2214.361	181.5313	12.19823	0.0000
R-squared	0.739961			
Adjusted R-squared	0.687225			
F-statistic	9.135103		Durbin-Watson	0.878030
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002			

Source: Authors' computation (2024)

Cochrane Orcutt Result

Higher-order autoregressive schemes are estimated using the Cochrane-Orcutt iterative approach. When the "Durbin Watson statistics" are extremely low in the OLS estimate, breaking the assumption of independent errors, it is utilized to adjust for autocorrelation in regression analysis. After applying the Cochrane-Orcutt approach, autocorrelation—which had previously been observed in the OLS in Table 5—was removed (Abang, Ayodel & Obafemi 2024). Table 5 presents the empirical outcome of the calculated regression line, which indicates whether or not the variables have produced the proper expected signals. The positive intercept of the computed regression line, shown below, is 28.75. This indicates that the real gross domestic product will automatically rise by 28.75 percent even if all explanatory factors remain the same.

The outcome demonstrates a positive correlation between Nigeria's actual gross domestic product and the exchange rate (EXR). This indicates a linear relationship

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between them. This is in line with theoretical predictions, which state that, *ceteris paribus*, a 10% increase in the exchange rate results in a 149.00% increase in real GDP domestic product.

The real gross domestic product (RGDP) and credit to the private sector (PCE) have a negative connection, indicating an inverse relationship. The RGDP will fall by 80.5% for every 10% rise in private consumption spending. The outcome also demonstrates that the inflation rate and RGDP are negatively correlated. This is also in line with theoretical expectations, which state that, *ceteris paribus*, a 10% increase in the inflation rate results in a 148.03% decline in RGDP. The findings indicate a negative correlation between interest rates and real gross domestic product. Therefore, a 10 percent increase in interest rates will result in a 119.37% drop in real gross domestic product.

According to statistical analysis, the real gross domestic product (RGDP), inflation (INF), and private consumption expenditure (PCE) all have a statistically significant impact on Nigeria's GDP. This is because the 0.05 level of significance is exceeded by their respective probability values of 0.00, 0.04, and 0.03. This indicates that these factors have a major impact on Nigeria's RGDP. However, because the probability value of 0.22 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, the interest rate is not statistically significant. The computed regression line fits the data well, as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.79. Specifically, the modified R-squared value of 0.77 indicates that changes in the explanatory factors account for around 77% of the total variations in the dependent variables. This indicates that the explanatory power of the calculated regression equation is high.

Likewise, the total model is statistically significant, as indicated by the *f*-statistics value of 37.61. This is because, at the five percent significance level, the calculated *F*-statistics value of 37.61 is higher than the crucial value. This indicates that the dependent variable is influenced by the independent factors jointly. A strong degree of linearity between the dependent and independent variables is also demonstrated by the model's overall significance.

The second-order test, often known as the econometric test, is used to ascertain whether autocorrelation exists in the model. To check for serial correlation in the model, the Durbin-Watson (DW) statistics are used in this investigation. There is no autocorrelation, as indicated by the Durbin-Watson value of 1.95. With a Durbin-

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Watson (D-W) score of 1.95, autocorrelation is absent. This implies that the results of this study can be used to formulate policies for the Nigerian economy.

Table 6: Cochrane Orcutt result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EXR	14.90076	13.02267	10.82018	0.0000
PCE	-8.005306	116.6352	-0.686354	0.0466
INF	-14.80268	116.0245	-0.903489	0.0318
INTR	-11.93672	487.0534	-1.256407	0.2164
C	28.74730	5871.062	4.896439	0.0000
R-squared	0.794114			
Adjusted R-squared	0.772998			
F-statistic	37.60635	Durbin-Watson stat		1.951434
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Diagnostic Test

The Q, LM, and heteroskedasticity tests A number of diagnostic tests were carried out to see whether the estimated equation was adequate. To determine whether the calculated model was stable, the Ramsey RESET test was used. To determine whether the estimated model was adequate or normal, normality tests, including the autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH) test and the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test, were used.

Table 7 provides a summary of the test outcomes. The estimated equation's stability was demonstrated by the Ramsey RESET test statistic of 1.543982 and its high probability value of 0.1362. With a high probability value of 0.4681 and a Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test statistic of 0.781764, the model was found to be autocorrelation-free. This suggests that there is no autocorrelation in the calculated

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equation because the residual terms are independent. The fact that the Chi-square probability value of 0.8660 is more than the 5% level of significance further supports this.

With a high probability of 0.0805, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test value of 1.56843 demonstrated that there is no heteroskedasticity issue and that the disturbance terms are therefore normally distributed. This is thus supported by the fact that the observed Chi-squared's probability value of 0.8660 is higher than the significance level of 5%. Furthermore, the observed R-squared Chi-square probability value of 0.1604 and the autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH) test value of 1.968697 with its high probability of 0.1694 are both greater than the 5% level of significance, indicating that autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity are not an issue.

Similarly, the Q-statistics in table 8 demonstrated that the series is white noise; therefore, since all of the probability values are greater than the 5 percent significance level, there is no autocorrelation among the residual components in the model. This means that the residual's value in one period was unrelated to the residual terms' value in another and also suggested that there was no covariation among the residuals. The estimated equation is sufficient and behaves well, according to the results of the many tests that were performed.

Table 7: Diagnostic test

Test Statistic	Value (prob.)		
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	0.781764	Prob. F (2,22)	0.9198
Obs. R-squared	2.406568	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.8660
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test			
F-statistic	1.56843	Prob. F(13,24)	0.0805
Obs. R-squared	21.53812	Prob. Chi-Square(13)	0.3991
Autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH)			
F-statistic	1.968697	Prob. F(1,35)	0.1694
Obs. R-squared	1.970364	Prob. Chi-Square(13)	0.1604
Ramsey RESET Test			
F-statistic	2.383879		0.1362

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10 (2024)

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Table 8: Q-Statistic Test

	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob*
1	0.047	0.047	0.0895	0.765
2	-0.034	-0.036	0.1370	0.934
3	-0.225	-0.223	2.3431	0.504
4	-0.204	-0.196	4.2060	0.379
5	-0.020	-0.028	4.2238	0.518
6	-0.034	-0.104	4.2772	0.639
7	0.270	0.198	7.8445	0.347
8	0.105	0.056	8.3984	0.396
9	0.017	0.000	8.4136	0.493
10	-0.246	-0.193	11.694	0.306
11	-0.119	-0.011	12.493	0.328
12	-0.048	-0.039	12.626	0.397
13	0.025	-0.022	12.664	0.474
14	0.056	-0.090	12.865	0.537
15	-0.078	-0.177	13.270	0.581
16	0.062	-0.002	13.540	0.633

Source: Author's computation using E-views 10 (2024)

Stability test

After the OLS models were estimated, the parameter's stability was examined using the Cumulative Sum (CUMSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUMSUM SQ) tests. The CUMSUM and CUSUM SQ test statistics are within the necessary bounds of \pm five percent level of significance, as shown in Figures 6 and 7. These plots show that there is a long-term correlation between Nigeria's economic growth and the structure of its financial system and that the coefficients of the results being estimated are steady during the 1980–2023 timeframe. Thus, this suggests that the coefficients are progressively changing.

FIG. 5: CUSUM test

FIG. 6: CUSUM of Square test

4.3 Discussion of findings

PCE has a long-term negative impact on economic growth that is statistically significant. Debt or other unsustainable sources are used to fuel excessive expenditure. Additional factors contributing to the negative impacts include inequality, resource misallocation, and dependency on imports, which can lead to trade deficits and impede local economic progress. This result is consistent with research by Alem and Soderbo (2010), Wadal (2011), and Nwabueze (2009). The result also shows a negative correlation between inflation and economic growth. Consequently, for every 10% increase in inflation, economic growth will fall by 148.03%. This is because inflation lowers consumer purchasing power, which lowers consumption and creates uncertainty that makes it hard for businesses to forecast future expenses and income, which lowers investment. The findings of Barro (1995), Chimobi (2010), and Chude & Chude (2015) are all in agreement with this outcome.

In a similar vein, the rate coefficient becomes negative. Therefore, interest rates and economic growth in Nigeria are inversely correlated. According to the results,

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economic growth will decrease by 119.38% *ceteris paribus* for every 10% increase in interest rates. The negative link implies that higher interest rates will result in higher borrowing costs, lower spending, and lower demand, which will cause the currency to appreciate and raise the cost of exports while lowering demand. Also, a rise in interest rates will lower consumer confidence, which will result in lower expenditure.

In addition, the results demonstrate a favorable correlation between the exchange rate and economic growth. Economic growth will increase by 149% for every 10% increase in the exchange rate. The positive link and its implications for economic growth can be attributed to the fact that it lowers the cost of exports, which raises demand and accelerates economic growth. As a result, a competitive and stable exchange rate promotes trade, which raises imports and exports and supports economic expansion. Similarly, a positive association might assist lower inflation and boost government revenue by increasing export-related tax collections.

Summary, conclusion, and policy recommendations

The main objective of this study was to analyse the impact of inflation and private consumption expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to examine the impact of inflation and private consumption expenditures on economic growth in Nigeria. To achieve the above objectives, empirical techniques based on the unit root testing procedure using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) were adopted to test for the stationarity of the variables. The study used annual data that spanned from 1980 to 2023 and adopted the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and several estimation tests like the unit root test, the cointegration test and the Granger causality test. The specified equations were estimated, and the following summaries of findings were presented.

While the conclusions of the literature reviewed were not entirely consistent, this study was able to close the research gap and investigate how Nigeria's currency rate, private consumption spending, interest rate, and inflation rate behaved by using data on a few important variables from 1980 to 2023. From the investigation, several conclusions were reached. The p-value showed that, in accordance with the traditional least squares result, only the exchange rate had a positive and significant impact on economic growth. The result showed that RGDP benefited from an increase in the exchange rate. It also showed a negative correlation between real GDP and interest rates, inflation, and private consumer expenditure.

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Conclusion

The study investigated the connection between Nigeria's economic growth, private consumption spending, and inflation. The Granger Causality test, the Phillips-Perron test, and the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test were all used in the study along with the regular least square's regression analysis technique. Assessing the effect of inflation on Nigeria's economic growth and figuring out how private consumption expenditures affect it were the primary goals of this study.

The time series data used covered a forty-four-year period, from 1980 to 2023. From the analysis, there was no autocorrelation in the result, according to the Durbin-Watson finding. While there is no causative relationship between the inflation rate and real gross domestic product, the Granger causality test demonstrates a uni-causal relationship between the exchange rate, interest rate, private consumption spending, and exchange rate and real gross domestic product.

Tests of the effects of both inflation and private consumption expenditure on economic growth variables revealed that they have a significant impact on Nigeria's real gross domestic product. As a result, the null hypotheses that inflation and private consumption expenditure (PCE) have no effect on economic growth in Nigeria, were rejected, and the alternative—that they do—were accepted.

Policy recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made to cause the increase of economic growth in Nigeria:

- i. Boost private consumption spending: Since private consumption makes up a sizable amount of aggregate demand, the Nigerian government should implement policies that will aid in raising consumption.
- ii. The government should figure out how to keep inflation under control to prevent consumers' purchasing power from declining.

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